

The EBiSC iPSC bank for disease studies

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

iPSC
EBiSC
Induced
Pluripotent
Stem
Cell
Europe
Biobank

ABSTRACT

The European Bank for induced Pluripotent Stem Cells (EBiSC), a non-profit repository for storage, banking, Quality Control (QC) and subsequent distribution of research-grade human induced Pluripotent Stem Cell (iPSC) lines, has centralised iPSC lines generated internationally across > 35 disease areas and made them available to users via the EBiSC Catalogue, for research use (cells.ebisc.org/). Comprehensive datasets are accessible prior to purchase detailing the disease background of the original tissue sample, background of iPSC reprogramming and cell line characterisation data. EBiSC also performs robust QC screening to ensure supply of reliable, well-characterised iPSC lines, compliant with ISO9001:2015 principles. Whole Genome Sequencing data for specific iPSC lines can be downloaded from the European Genome Archive, subject to application to the EBiSC Data Access Committee. The EBiSC Access and Use Agreement, required to be completed prior to shipping, can be downloaded from the website along with specific Cell Line Information Packs; together these documents clarify how EBiSC lines can be used for research and detail any specific Third Party Obligations and/or restrictions for use which may apply. A protocol for how to culture and monitor iPSC lines including implementation of routine cell line screening is also available. A second project phase will continue collecting iPSC lines generated internationally, provide iPSC derived differentiated products using improved automation strategies for upscaling and develop the current services provided by EBiSC, including iPSC reprogramming, gene-editing and characterisation.

1. The European Bank for induced Pluripotent Stem Cells

As the use of human induced Pluripotent Stem Cell (iPSC) lines within disease research has accelerated dramatically since their creation in 2006 (Takahashi and Yamanaka, 2006), demand across the research community for stable, well characterised iPSC lines generated from diverse disease, ethnic and genetic backgrounds has risen correspondingly. The European Bank for induced Pluripotent Stem Cells (EBiSC) was established in 2014 as a non-profit repository for storage, banking, Quality Control (QC) and subsequent distribution of research-grade iPSC lines (Fig. 1). Essential for its success, EBiSC was established, and is currently in a second project phase as, a public-private partnership supported by the Innovative Medicines Initiative Joint Undertaking (IMI-JU) and the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA). The collaborative nature of this partnership enables EBiSC to collect expertise from commercial, academic and SME partners, pooling scientific excellence in the generation,

characterisation and downstream use of iPSCs for disease modelling and drug discovery. Early establishment of EBiSC central facilities and associated standard protocols was accelerated through EBiSC consortium members actively contributing to building the repository (De Sousa et al., 2017a, 2017b). Collaboration with other iPSC research projects (e.g. StemBANCC, HipSci and IMI-ADAPTED) and implementation of a selective cell line generation programme, aiming to generate and make available iPSC lines from which there was demand across the academic and commercial researcher landscape, has subsequently built a diverse repository. Over the last 5 years, > 19 research groups across Europe and the United States have deposited their iPSC lines into EBiSC, helping to develop efficient and robust processes for cell line deposition, banking, Quality Control (QC) and end user distribution. At the time of writing, iPSC lines from > 35 disease areas are available, including Alzheimer's, Parkinson's and Huntington's diseases, genetic Cardiac diseases and rare disorders such as Bardet-Biedl and Dravet syndromes, as well as healthy controls. Non-integrating

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scr.2020.102034>

Received 31 May 2019; Received in revised form 6 December 2019; Accepted 5 October 2020

Available online 09 October 2020

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Fig. 1. Building the European Bank for induced Pluripotent Stem Cells. EBiSC is dependent on the individuals who donate tissue samples to support disease research and the international iPSC researchers who generate, characterise and then share iPSC lines with EBiSC (red). Upon receipt of an application to deposit iPSC lines, a number of aspects including cell line suitability, consent and characterisation data are reviewed by EBiSC prior to completion of a deposit agreement (blue). Deposited lines undergo banking, Quality Control and distribution under a robust Quality Management system (green). A second project stage, EBiSC2, will further support iPSC scientists and progress disease research through provision of differentiated progenitors, mature cell models, ready to use formats and assess feasibility to generate iPSC lines suitable for commercial use (multi). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

reprogramming using Sendai CytoTune™ accounts for the vast majority of lines (82.4%) with Episomal and Retroviral vectors (8.1% and 7.9% respectively) also commonly used. Cohorts of gene-edited isogenic variant iPSC lines are available across multiple disease areas and genotypes, including gene knockouts and reporters. Deposited iPSC lines are available to users through the EBiSC catalogue (cells.ebisc.org/), subject to completion of an Access and Use Agreement (AUA) and a nominal fee to maintain not for profit operations of the bank long-term.

A second project phase supported by IMI-2 and EFPIA (EBiSC2) started in March 2019 with a core goal of ensuring that the governance framework and iPSC processing infrastructure established between 2014 and 2017 is sustainable and fully operable long-term. Detailed in section 4, EBiSC2 will develop additional products and services to progress and accelerate iPSC research internationally, in addition to ensuring efficient data management and distribution of iPSCs and associated products.

2. Depositing iPSC lines into EBiSC

Through collaboration with clinical centres, EBiSC iPSC lines have been generated by commercial, academic and non-profit institutions across Europe and North America and shared with EBiSC through completion of consent review (2.1), signature of an EBiSC Material Deposit Agreement (2.2) and collection of iPSC datasets (2.3, Fig. 1). Application to deposit lines into EBiSC is initiated simply by contacting EBiSC via the EBiSC website (<https://cells.ebisc.org/>).

2.1. Consent review

Initial learnings emphasised to EBiSC the importance of assuring use of suitable consent templates and agreeing cell line ownership early in the deposition process. All tissue samples from which EBiSC iPSC lines are derived must have been collected under consent permissive for iPSC generation, characterisation and wide distribution to academic and

commercial users for research purposes. Use of the DISCUSS principles (Lomax et al., 2013) have been instrumental in the review of historical consent forms under which tissue samples were collected prior to the wide adoption of iPSC technology, for which most consent forms collecting human biosamples now accommodate for. Ethical advisors and experts within EBiSC agreed that, in line with DISCUSS, iPSC lines should be considered as part of the standard set of research tools for disease modelling and drug discovery as long as iPSC generation is not specifically precluded by text in the consent documents and consent is permissive for other aspects of downstream use (Morrison et al., 2017). This approach enabled the use of valuable biosamples in disease research and minimised the need for re-consenting. As an additional measure, EBiSC developed consent templates with a favourable ethical opinion which explicitly cover iPSC generation, genomic analysis and unknown future research techniques, allowing future use of collected samples for research methods which cannot be foreseen at the time of sample collection. This approach is essential to maximise use of donated tissue samples which individuals have gifted to researchers in order to accelerate disease research and have already been used across other IMI funded research programmes to accelerate biosample collection and iPSC generation.

2.2. EBiSC material deposit agreement

iPSC lines are deposited into EBiSC by the ‘owner’ of the iPSC line, commonly the institution(s) responsible for collection of the primary material and/or the derivation of the iPSC line(s). EBiSC recommends that rights for deposition are defined early on in iPSC research projects, simplifying latter cell line deposition. In addition to securing their research resource(s) long-term and supporting international research efforts, cell line depositors are recognised through use of the hPSCreg cell line nomenclature system (Kurtz et al., 2018) and gain access to EBiSC lines and associated datasets. Through completion of the EBiSC Material Deposit Agreement, the Depositor agrees that the applicable iPSC

lines can be distributed by EBiSC to commercial and non-profit users for research use, with fee for service activities specifically precluded, requiring a separate agreement between relevant parties. During the deposition process, cell line owners are responsible for declaring any restrictions for use and/or obligations to third party licencing which must be passed onto cell line users. Third party obligations (TPOs) such as these are explicitly listed in the deposit agreement and passed onto users using a Cell Line Information Pack (CLIP), publically available on the EBiSC website for user review prior to purchase.

2.3. Collection of iPSC line characterisation data

Use of iPSCs for disease research is reliant on having comprehensive datasets on the disease status of the donor and the generation and characterisation of the generated iPSC line(s). Anonymised information on the provenance of the iPSC line is collected into the hPSCreg data portal, hPSCreg.eu, (Seltmann et al., 2016) and is publically available on both the EBiSC catalogue and hPSCreg prior to cell line purchase. This includes *i) the background of the donor* such as known disease association(s), disease associated genotype(s), donor sex, related publications, and where suitable, clinical information or links to managed access clinical data repositories can be found; *ii) Collection and derivation of the primary material* such as tissue type collected, donor age range at the time of tissue collection and derivation of resulting cell lines such as Fibroblast lines; *iii) History of iPSC generation* including, critically, if the line has been published previously, the reprogramming technology, method of cell line selection used and all culture methods including if feeder cells and/or reagents such as Rho Kinase inhibitors were used at any point during iPSC derivation; *iv) Details of gene-editing (if applicable)* including the gene-editing technology used (for example, CRISPR-Cas9, TALENs, ZFNs etc), the type of modification performed such as correction of an isogenic mutation or vice-versa etc, and of course the specific gene and chromosomal location which was targeted and resulting genotype; *v) Cell line characterisation data* provided by depositors typically includes a record of cell line identity, iPSC morphology, expression of markers representative for iPSC identity, potential for differentiation to early germ layers and/or maturation to specific cell populations, chromosomal health using methods such as G-Banding and/or Single Nucleotide Polymorphism arrays and absence of microbiological agents including Mycoplasma and human viral pathogens HIV1, HIV2, HBV and HCV.

3. EBiSC Banking, Quality Control and iPSC distribution

Centralised iPSC banking and QC standardises iPSC lines which have been derived by multiple institutions (3.1, 3.2), with key datasets are available via the EBiSC catalogue prior to distribution. Terms of use and any applicable restrictions are also publically available, allowing for iPSC lines from multiple sources to be transferred under a single agreement (3.3), with training resources aiming to ensure best practice during downstream use, (3.4, Fig. 1).

3.1. EBiSC Quality Control

Original datasets are supplemented by EBiSC generated data through completion of strict batch release testing and informational cell line characterisation. Batch release testing ensures the safety and provenance of EBiSC lines using high-sensitivity sterility and Mycoplasma screening, post-cryopreservation viability, absence of human viral pathogens (if data is not provided by the Depositor) and confirmation of the cell line identity using Short Tandem Repeat screening. Informational testing then provides an overview of the phenotype and suitability of each line for downstream use, to aid the user's cell line selection. This includes flow cytometry of key pluripotency and self-renewal markers POU5F1, SSEA-4, SSEA-1 and TRA-1-60, potential for *in vitro* trilineage differentiation, assessment of chromosomal health

using G-Banding and/or Single Nucleotide Polymorphism arrays, vector clearance and in the case of gene-edited lines, characterisation of the modified locus. In some instances, Whole Genome Sequencing data may be generated which is then available to users through application to the [EBiSC Data Access Committee](#). Generated datasets are available to users both prior to and subsequent to, cell line purchase. Batch specific culture recommendations and qualification data are detailed on a Certificate of Analysis, available to users after cell line purchase.

3.2. EBiSC expansion and banking

EBiSC iPSC lines are cultured and banked using defined feeder-free culture methods (mTeSRTM1 or Essential-8 and Matrigel/GeltrexTM or Vitronectin) and deposited iPSC lines generated in other media/matrix combinations are adapted to one of these culture systems prior to cell line banking. Cells are cryopreserved at 1-2x10⁶ cells/vial in DMSO based cryopreservant. EBiSC banking and QC activities are performed by experienced teams at EBiSC central facilities, namely the Fraunhofer Institute for Biomedical Engineering, also responsible for maintaining the EBiSC Mirror Bank which secures long-term storage of all deposited iPSC lines, and The European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures. Established Quality Management Systems compliant with ISO9001:2015 underpin central operations across both institutions.

3.3. iPSC line selection and distribution

Users can view all available iPSC lines and associated datasets at cells.ebisc.org, including reviewing the CLIP which details any cell line specific restrictions and/or TPOs and then proceed to purchase through the ECACC catalogue. The EBiSC AUA and relevant CLIP must be completed by an authorised signatory who has formal authority to undertake legal obligations on behalf of the user. It was acknowledged at the outset of EBiSC that access to iPSC lines is often burdensome, requiring multiple complicated transfer agreements and lengthy negotiations across multiple institutions. As one of EBiSC's main goals is to increase the accessibility of high quality iPSC cell lines, EBiSC has strived to simplify this process through completion of a single AUA and cell line specific CLIPs, allowing for acquisition of iPSC lines from multiple sources simultaneously.

Once the AUA and CLIPs are received by the main distributor ECACC, the user can proceed with cell line purchase, shipment and receipt. The AUA permits use of EBiSC iPSC lines for research use with the following conditions; a) clinical applications, human cloning and 'fee for service' activities are currently specifically precluded; b) local laws and regulations must be adhered to; and c) any TPOs, licencing restrictions or consent based restrictions must be respected (detailed in the relevant CLIP). Users are charged a nominal fee for each cell line vial purchased to sustain EBiSC operations long term, allowing EBiSC to maintain cell line stocks, perform QC as required and continue allowing researchers to deposit new iPSC lines into EBiSC. In addition to each vial purchased, users gain access to support materials and comprehensive datasets, supporting users to maximise use of their iPSC lines. After cell line receipt, users receive guidance on safe handling of the shipment and frozen vial(s) and recommendations for long-term storage to ensure cell line viability is retained until iPSC culture is initiated. Batch specific Certificates of Analysis can be accessed on the ECACC website using the batch ID supplied on the relevant EBiSC cryovial(s).

3.4. EBiSC user support

A core goal of EBiSC is to ensure that iPSC research is simplified and accessible to all researchers, regardless of experience. In addition to enabling generation and use of iPSCs, EBiSC supplies training and 'best practice' resources across the community. A series of workshops and hands-on cell culture training sessions held between 2014 and 2017 were attended by both consortium members and non-members,

focusing on core techniques such as aseptic cell handling and cell line thawing, to more complex aspects such as initiating and monitoring neuronal and cardiac iPSC differentiation and performing gene-editing. An associated cell culture manual is publically available at <https://cells.ebisc.org/> to support users in maintaining best practice during culture of their iPSC lines, with clear guidance on evaluating iPSC line stability through visual assessments of confluency, morphology and spontaneous differentiation as well as recommendations for QC which should be performed routinely by the user to maintain high quality cell line stocks.

4. EBiSC2: Reaching long term sustainability

A second project phase focused on building long-term self-sustainability of EBiSC was launched in March 2019. Focused on cementing sustainable operations after completion of the project period, EBiSC2 will expand the range of available iPSC lines and derivatives which are available, including assessing the feasibility of distributing EBiSC iPSC lines for commercial use, see Fig. 1. Although the EBiSC catalogue has and is being built to meet user demand, the ever shifting landscape of genetic disease research ensures that no biobank can ever be fully comprehensive. With this in mind, EBiSC2 can help researchers generate new iPSC lines if suitable lines are not already available in the Catalogue. With an established network of iPSC centres, EBiSC2 acts as an intermediary between users and iPSC centres to facilitate service provision of iPSC line generation, gene-editing, differentiation, banking and QC. EBiSC derived lines are made available through the Catalogue along with QC and characterisation datasets (with sensitive data accessible through the EBiSC Data Access Committee). Building on the successful collaborations with other iPSC centred research programmes in the first project phase, iPSC researchers can continue to deposit their iPSC lines into EBiSC, ensuring secure long-term storage of their lines at the EBiSC2 mirror bank, gaining recognition for them and their institutions and supporting other iPSC scientists with progressing their research, whilst retaining intellectual property rights on lines they have generated. Processes to streamline the deposit of iPSC lines generated within other international iPSC research programmes will be further developed, securing long-term storage of these vital resources after project completion and providing a solution for long term project sustainability. Automated processes established within the first project phase will be transferred across multiple EBiSC workflows to increase efficiencies and enable supply of iPSC and differentiated progenitors in bulk. iPSC derived cell models for neurological and cardiac disorders will be developed, including, where appropriate, the use of co-cultures to drive differentiation and maturation. The scientific and clinical network established within the first project phase will be utilised to enable collection of patient samples and associated clinical datasets for use in drug discovery.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Rachel Steeg: Conceptualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Project administration. **Julia C. Neubauer:** Visualization, Supervision, Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sabine C. Müller:** Writing - review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Andreas Ebneith:** Visualization, Supervision, Writing - review & editing, Funding

acquisition, Conceptualization. **Heiko Zimmermann:** Visualization, Supervision, Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

EBiSC – The European Bank for induced pluripotent Stem Cells project has received support from the Innovative Medicines Initiative Joint Undertaking under grant agreement n° 115582 and from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 821362, resources of which are composed of financial contribution from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013), European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and EFPIA.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scr.2020.102034>.

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